

Short Communication

Qualitative Analysis of the Phyto-Chemical Properties of Selected Tomato Varieties

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Abstract

This work was carried out to qualitatively analyze the phyto-chemical properties of selected tomato varieties. Three tomato varieties were procured and separately subjected to laboratory analysis. The laboratory analysis was carried out at the bio-medicinal laboratory center of the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan. The following phyto-chemical properties were assessed: Saponins, Tannins, Alkaloid, Falconoid, Anthraquinones, and Cardiac glycosides. The result of the laboratory shows that out of the three varieties of tomato; beefsteak has the highest phyto-chemical properties. The phyto-chemical constituents of the three varieties are as follows: Beefsteak tomatoes contain saponins, tannins, flabonoids, anthaquinones and cardiac glycoside. Roma contain saponin, tannins, and cardiac glycoside, while cherry contain three properties of phyto-chemical which are saponins, tannin, and cardiac glycoside. The result shows that the morphological trait of the three tomatoes varieties, in terms, of weight, size, shape and the thickness of their pericarp. Beefsteak has the weight of about 63.3g, round pointed tip, shape size of 6.5cm and the thickness of the pericarp is 0.2mm, the roma has a weight of 38.33g, its oval in shape, it has a size of 3.1cm while three thickness of its pericarp is 0.07mm, cherry tomato has the weight of 21.6g, its oblong in shape, and it has a size of 2.0cm, and the thickness of its pericarp is 0.1mm. From the study, it can be concluded that there are considerable differences in the phyto-chemical properties of tomato varieties.

Keyword: Phyto-chemical, Tomato, Laboratory analysis, Varieties, Screening.

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Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crops grown all over Nigeria. In Nigeria, tomato is regarded as the most important vegetable after onions and pepper (Fawusi, 1978). Tomato is classified as a functional food, for having high levels of vitamins and minerals. It is an important condiment in most diets and a very cheap source of vitamins. It also contains a large quantity of water, calcium and niacin which are of great importance in the metabolic activities of man. Tomato is a source of vitamins A, C and E that are very good for body and protect the body against diseases (Taylor, 1987).

Tomato contains a variety of phyto-chemical constituents including carotenoids, phenols, tannin, flavonoid, alkaloid, saponin, phytates (Omodamiro and Amechi, 2013). The prominent carotenoids in tomatoes are lycopene, a pigment principally responsible for deep red color of tomato fruits and tomato products. Tomato is also a major source of antioxidants contributing to the daily intake of a significant amount of beneficial molecules, such as B-carotene, a precursor of vitamin A, lycopene (85%), ascorbic acid, tocopherols, phytoene, phytofluene, provitamin A, polyphenols including quercetin, nutrients like folate vit-C, vit-E, vit-K vit-B, phosphorus, sulphur, potassium, calcium, iron (significant quantities), sugars like aldoses, ketoses, disaccharides, polysaccharides mainly starch, proteins and amino acids phytosterol like cholesterol, sitosterol and small quantities of fats flavonoid and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives (Clinton, 1998; Abushita, 2000). All of these components are known to contribute significantly to the antioxidant activity of tomato fruit resulting in a combined protective effect on human. Tomato also contains other protective mechanisms, such as antithrombotic and anti-inflammatory functions.

Tomato is a major crop in vegetable industry in Nigeria and also an important ingredient in food production and processing in the country. Tomatoes contribute to a healthy, well-balanced diet (Naika, 2005), as they are rich in minerals, vitamins, essential amino acids, sugars, dietary fibers, vitamin B and C, iron and phosphorus. In Nigeria, tomato is processed into different products including: tomato paste, powder and dry fruits (Ugonna 2015). Although, the nutritional composition such as the phyto-chemical constituents of tomato is well documented (Ojiako and Igwe, 2008; Rai 2012), little or no information is known about the phyto-chemical compositions of the fruits of several tomato varieties common in Nigerian market. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the phyto-chemical constituents present in the selected tomato varieties.

Materials and Methods

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The study was carried out in anti-biomedical laboratory center of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan. It is located in Ibadan North-West Local Government area of Oyo state. The climate condition of the area is tropically dominated by rainfall pattern ranging from 1400mm-1500mm; the average temperature is above 35.2°C (FRIN, ANNUAL METROLOGICAL REPORT).

Procurement of Materials

Three varieties were obtained from the market (Bodija market) Ibadan. Other materials like Weighing balance, Water bath were obtained at the Bio-medicinal laboratory (FRIN), Ibadan.

Method

One (1) sizeable number of Tomato fruit was separated from each class, rinsed and crushed with mortar and pestle then, small portion of the sample was taken with syringe into a clean beaker and 1g was weighted inside another beaker then 10ml of distil water was added to it and boiled inside the water bath for 10 minute. The procedure was repeated for the other two (2) varieties and the beaker containing each samples was labeled to be Beafsteak, Roma and Cherry.

Table 1: Parameter Assessed

Boiled for 10minutes ROMA SCREENING	PHYTOCHEMICAL	
1. SAPONINS:		
Frothing test: 0.5g of sample + 10ml of distill water shaken for 20 minutes.	Persistence foam was observed.	Positive
Emulsifying test: 0.5 of the sample + 2 drops of olive oil.	There was a stable emulsion.	Positive
2. ALKALOIDS		
0.5g of sample + 10ml of H ₂ O + Feric Acid + HCL boiled and filtered.	No colour changed.	Negative
3. TANNINS		
0.4g of sample + 10ml of H ₂ O boiled and filtered, filtrate + 2 drops of Ferric chloride.	Green colour was observed.	Negative
4. FLAVONOIDS		
0.5g of sample + NAOH + HCL	No formation was observed	Negative
5. ANTHRAQUINONES		
00.5g of sample + 5ml of	No colour change	

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chloroform, shaken for 10minutes then filtered, filtereate + 5ml NH3 + NAOH + HCL		Negative
6. CARDIAC GLYCOSIDES		
0.5g of sample + 10ml of ethanol boiled for 10 minutes	Brown ring colour was observed.	Positive

Table 2: Phyto-chemical screening on the Three Varieties of Tomato

Varieties	Photochemical Properties					
	Saponins	Alkaloids	Tannins	Flavonoids	Anthraquinones	Cardiac glycoside
Beefsteak	+	-	+	+	+	+
Roma	+	-	+	-	-	+
Cherry	+	-	+	+	-	+

+ means positive or present
- means negative or absent

Table 1 shows that the sample have positive results indicating presence of saponins and cardiac glycosides, while the negative results depicts absence of the phytochemicals. Table 2 shows that the value of phyto-chemical properties of each variety from the table, Beefsteak has the highest phyto-chemical properties of Five (5), Roma has three (3), while Cherry also has three (3). The results in this study, compared with previous results ().

Conclusion

Based on the findings, three varieties of tomato contain the following constituent, beefsteak with the highest constituent contain more of saponins, tannins, flavonoids anthraquinones and cardia glycoside while alkanoids was absent, Roma contain only saponins tannins and cardiac glycosides while, Alkanoids, Flavonoids and Anthraquinone are absent, cherry contain saponins, Cardiac glycosides and small quantity of Flavonoids and saponins while tannins Anthraquinone and Alkanoids were absent.

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